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Flow Behaviour of Bentonite Suspension. Part-II. Interaction with Inorganic and Organic Polyions

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THE protective and sensitising effect of hydrophilic colloids on hydrophobic sol has been known for long time but the detailed study with respect to interaction of polyelectrolytes with clay suspension is yet to be undertaken. This provides one of the ways of probing the mechanism involved in such process. Kajisaki *et al.*¹ studied the effect of K-polyacrylate as a deflocculant which increased

the plasticity to some degree. Joyce and Worrall² studied the adsorption of polyphosphate on two kaolinitic clays and found that adsorption is mainly physical rather than anion-exchange in nature. Bentonite clay is more sensitive towards aqueous phase interaction in comparison to other clays and is one of the best varieties available in India.

Experimental

Bihar bentonite clay, collected in lump form, was purified³ from the associated impurities like quartz, feldspar, calcite, organic matters and water soluble alkali salts and a definite size fraction (1 μ and below) was collected. Purified Bihar bentonite was converted into Na-form and its characteristics are as follows: constituents (% w/w) SiO₂, 51.30; Al₂O₃, 21.31; Fe₂O₃, 1.41; MgO, 1.36; loss on ignition, 14.89; cation exchange capacity (meq/100 g) 97.20; DTA peak temp. (°C), 155, 565 (endo), 940 (exo).

Solution of each of the polyelectrolytes, like Na-silicate, Na-hexametaphosphate, Na-polyacrylate, Na-amylose phosphate, Na-lauryl sulphate, polyvinyl alcohol, gelatin and Na-carboxymethylcellulose, was added in increasing amounts to 10% Na-bentonite suspension for study of its rheological behaviour. The plastic viscosity and yield value were determined in a modified McMichael viscometer utilising Reiner and Rewlin equation⁴ for plastic flow in a rotational viscometer as a function of addition of polyelectrolytes.

Results and Discussion

The interaction of the macromolecular compounds with bentonite is quite different from that of electrolytes as studied and reported in a previous communication⁵. The yield value and plastic viscosity values are given in Table I.

Plastic viscosity was found to increase on addition of polyelectrolytes as compared to the original value without any addition. Inorganic polyions, Na-carboxymethyl cellulose and Na-polyacrylate showed continuous increase of plastic viscosity. Viscosity is very much dependent on solvent-solute interaction. Na-carboxymethylcellulose is very much susceptible to polymerisation and a very good complexing agent for Al³⁺ which resides at the edge of the clay crystal and is responsible for the positive charge. Amongst the inorganic dispersing agents, sodium silicate is a more effective polymerising material. The viscosity was minimum with Na-lauryl sulphate although Na-lauryl sulphate and polyvinyl alcohol behave in the same fashion—the viscosity initially increased, reached a maximum and sharply decreased. Rapid decrease of viscosity might be due to the decrease in solvent-solute interaction resulting in coagulation of the system. But in the case of amylose phosphate and gelatin, the viscosity increased on

TABLE 1 - PLASTIC VISCOSITY AND YIELD VALUE OF 10% Na-BENTONITE SUSPENSION DURING INTERACTION WITH DIFFERENT POLYELECTROLYTES

Polyelectrolyte added	Parameter*	Volume of 10% solution added to 100 ml 10% Na-bentonite suspension (ml)				
		2	5	10	20	30
Na-silicate	A	17.8	16.84	20.62	27.17	36.67
	B	0	0	0	0	0.034 12
Na-hexametaphosphate	A	15.63	16.54	17.74	18.04	20.74
	B	0	0	0	0	0
Na-polyacrylate	A	14.31	15.73	18.42	20.32	24.92
	B	0	0	0	0	0.034 12
Na-amylose phosphate	A	16.84	16.54	17.03	18.04	17.88
	B	0	0	0	0	0.010 23
Na-lauryl sulphate	A	27.67	30.52	27.54	20.14	14.68
	B	0.617 7	0.655 2	0.515 3	0.484 6	0.143 3
Polyvinyl alcohol	A	23.09	26.46	25.25	20.65	14.21
	B	0.409 6	0.614 4	0.505 2	0.320 7	0
Gelatin	A	18.66	18.64	19.48	22.84	23.15
	B	0.129 3	0.211 5	0.430 0	0.532 3	0.430 0
Na-carboxymethyl cellulose	A	125.2	171.8	322.1	365.1	529.1
	B	3.924	1.536	3.242	4.266	9.725

*A = Plastic viscosity ($\times 10^3$ poise), B = yield value (dyne cm^{-1}).

progressive addition but in a stepwise manner and the change was not so significant.

Disappearance of yield value was observed with inorganic polyions—Na-polyacrylate and Na-amylose phosphate which is solely related to the mode of particle association and to the stability of the complex at the edge of the clay crystal. Amongst the polyions, Na-carboxymethylcellulose exhibited significantly high yield value which might be associated with the high degree of polymerisation of the reagent. The yield value in this case initially decreased followed by sharp rise on further addition. Some relationship with respect to yield value change was noticed with gelatin only upto 20 ml addition.

Thus it is noted that the stability of the 10% bentonite suspension on progressive addition of polyelectrolyte, which contains functional group distributed along the entire length of the chain, improved with silicate, hexametaphosphate, polyacrylate and amylose phosphate. In other cases, mode of particle association was such that it led to change of flow behaviour to non-Newtonian direction.

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Heat of Transport of Water in Soil Fractions, Model Soils and an Alluvial Soil

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SOME reports of studies on thermal diffusion of water in soil have appeared¹. Recently, Sanyal *et al.*²⁻⁴ have examined the phenomena of thermal diffusion in soil/clay systems. The present paper reports such thermally induced migrations in soil components isolated from an alluvial soil in order to examine the specific effects and then extend these experiments to 'model soil' composed thereof. The paper also reports the non-isothermal diffusion of water across the given alluvial soil for providing a comparison to results obtained with the synthetic soils.

Experimental

The soil used was an alluvial surface soil (0-15 cm) collected from Baruipur, 24-Parganas, West